

Human-Like motion planning in the Cartesian domain for robotic manipulators

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Abstract—Human-Likeness is an important feature to be implemented in robotic systems that have to interact and share the workspace with humans. Embedding this characteristic in robotic manipulators can improve the safety and effectiveness of human-robot interaction during human-robot interaction. Human motion has a peculiar set of features that are hardly matched via classical motion planning algorithms traditionally used in robotics. For this reason, there is a vivid interest in the research community for the development of novel approaches able to generate human-like motions. In the literature, there are two main ways to address this problem: 1) exploit neuroscientific findings to design a planning algorithm and 2) use learning-based approaches to teach the algorithm how human moves. However, these approaches may limit the variability of the computed motion or need for a large number of movements recorded. Starting from a previous work, where we proposed to exploit functional Principal Component Analysis (fPCA) to extract human motion features to embed directly in a joint-domain planner, in this paper we introduce a possible extension of this approach in the Cartesian domain. This new framework will permit us to solve some of the problems of its predecessor (i.e. generalization to different kinematic chains and computational time).

Index Terms—Human-like Motion generation, Planning algorithms, Human-Machine interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Human-likeness (HL) plays a crucial role in a secure, efficient, and reliable human-robot interaction. The generation of Human-Like movements remains an open challenge, yet it holds significant importance for enhancing realism, acceptability, and predictability for human users.

Human motion exhibits distinct key features that set it apart from movements generated by classical planning algorithms. A cornerstone of the generation of human-like movements is [1], where the authors observed that humans tend to minimize jerk during movement execution.

In literature, there are two main classes of Human-Like motion generation methods. The first exploit neuroscientific studies to define an optimization-based approach (for example in [2] the authors generate a trajectory minimizing the jerk of the trajectory itself). However, this type of strategy can be computationally demanding and can reduce the variability of the generated motions. The other way is to use data-driven approaches to learn Human-Like behaviour [3]. However, learning-based approaches usually require a lot of data to be able to generalize in different situations.

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A possible solution to the aforementioned problems is to embed HL directly in the planning algorithm. In [4], the authors analyzed human upper limb motions in the joint domain using functional Principal Component Analysis (fPCA). The extracted basis of functions can be combined to obtain an intrinsically Human-Like motion. However, the design of the algorithm in the joint domain brings two main limitations. First, the definition of obstacle in the joint space is not trivial and to solve the planning problem an optimization is required, whose solution usually requires several seconds. The other problem is the need for a mapping strategy to use this algorithm with different kinematic chains.

In this work, building on the results of motion analysis performed in [5], we propose an fPCA-based Human-Like planning algorithm defined in the Cartesian domain. First, we briefly describe the structure of the planning algorithm. Then we provide a proof of concept demonstration of our approach in terms of HL of the trajectories generated and we discuss future developments.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Functional Principal Component Analysis

Functional Principal Component Analysis (fPCA) is a statistical method to identify functional primitives from time-varying data. In this section, we will provide a brief introduction to the theory, while referring to [6] for more details. Let us assume a database of movements described in an N-dimensional space: $x(t) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ where $t \in [0, 1]$ is the normalized time. A generic hand motion $x(t)$ can then be decomposed in terms of the weighted sum of base elements $S_i(t)$, or functional Principal Components (fPCs):

$$x(t) \simeq \bar{x} + S_0(t) + \sum_{i=1}^{s_{\max}} \alpha_i \circ S_i(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha_i \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is a vector of weights, $S_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is the i^{th} basis element or fPC and s_{\max} is the number of basis elements considered. The operator \circ is the Hadamard product, $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$ is an average configuration extracted from data while $S_0 : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ is the average trajectory, aka *zero-order* fPC.

The output of fPCA, which is calculated independently for each dimension of the space, is a basis of functions $\{S_1, \dots, S_{s_{\max}}\}$ that maximizes the explained variance of the movements in the collected dataset. Given a dataset with M elements collecting the trajectories recorded in a given dimension j , the first fPC $S_{j,1}(t)$ is the function that solves the following problem

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{S_{j,1}} & \sum_{i=1}^M \left(\int S_{j,1}(t) x_j(t) dt \right)^2 \\ \text{subject to} & \|S_{j,1}(t)\|_2^2 = \int_0^1 S_{j,1}^2(t) dt = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Simulation of the task "Blocking the sun from face" with two obstacles

Subsequent fPCs $S_{j,i}(t)$ are, again, the functions that solve (2) with an additional orthogonality condition imposed by

$$\int_0^1 S_{j,i}(t)S_{j,p}(t)dt = 0, \forall p \in \{1, \dots, i-1\}. \quad (3)$$

B. Planning Algorithm

To build the planning algorithm we must first extract the fPCs from a dataset of human movements. To do this, we applied fPCA to a dataset containing human upper limb motions performing different activities of daily living [7]. For the sake of space, the results of this analysis are omitted, but the interested reader can find them in [5].

The idea is to exploit (1) to build a linear equation system to compute a set of weights α_i which solves the planning problem. In this way, we can easily compute in a closed form a trajectory with arbitrary initial and final conditions (such as position, velocity and acceleration). This solution can be also exploited to guarantee collision avoidance by selecting a set of viapoints to guide the trajectory around the obstacles. These additional constraints can be easily added to the planner by increasing the number of equations in the system and the number of fPCs involved.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

To perform some preliminary tests on this approach, we simulated a 7-DoF model of a human upper limb using the "Robotics Toolbox for MATLAB" developed by Peter Corke in MATLAB R2020b. To control the kinematic chain, we design a Cartesian computed torque controller

$$\tau = J^T M_X (\ddot{\xi}_d + K_V \dot{\xi} + K_P \xi) + h(q, \dot{q}) - J^T M_X J \dot{q} \quad (4)$$

where ξ_d , $\dot{\xi}_d$ and $\ddot{\xi}_d$ are Cartesian desired position, velocity and acceleration, $\xi = \xi - \xi_d$, $\dot{\xi} = \dot{\xi} - \dot{\xi}_d$, J is the Jacobian, M_X is the Cartesian generalized mass and $h(q, \dot{q})$ is the term related to gravity and coriolis effects.

To control the redundancy of the kinematic chain we design a secondary controller which has two main goals. The first is to push the arm away from the obstacles and avoid collision with the whole kinematic chain. The torque is generated by a set of repulsive forces distributed along the arm defined as:

$$\tau_{obs} = J_{elb}^T F_{elb} + J_{arm}^T F_{arm} + J_{forearm}^T F_{forearm} \quad (5)$$

where the single repulsive force is computed as:

$$F_i = \frac{\xi_i - \xi_{obs}}{\|\xi_i - \xi_{obs}\|} \cdot \frac{1}{d_i} \quad (6)$$

The second control input τ_{elb} is designed to keep the arm near a desired posture:

$$\tau_{elb} = -K_v \dot{q} + K_p (\bar{q} - q) \quad (7)$$

where \bar{q} is the desired arm posture. The overall control input is defined as:

$$\tau_{null} = P(\tau_{obs} + \tau_{elb}) \quad (8)$$

where $P = I - JJ^T$ is the Cartesian space null projector and it guarantees that this secondary controller does not affect the primary one.

For the simulation, we selected 5 different tasks from [7] and we tested them with different obstacle configurations evaluating the capability of the framework to solve the planning problem and to generate human-like movements. As an indicator of the HL, we computed the jerk of the trajectories. The results show that the proposed algorithm is able to compute a trajectory for all these scenarios. In terms of HL, the movement generated showed a low level of jerk both at the end-effector ($0.32m/s^3$ for the translation and $0.97rad/s^3$ for the rotation) and at the joint level ($0.78rad/s^3$).

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we introduced the idea of a novel planning algorithm in the Cartesian domain able to compute movement intrinsically Human-Like. This can be done by exploiting the results obtained from functional Principal Component Analysis applied to a dataset of human upper limb motion recorded during activities of daily living. We also showed some preliminary results that prove the effectiveness of this type of approach.

The next step will be to perform an extensive campaign of testing, where our planning algorithm is compared with other techniques already presented in the literature and deploy this approach on different platforms with different kinematic structures. After that, we will move to evaluate how much this framework can improve the perceived HL by human users during collaboration tasks both with classical manipulators and with humanoid robots.

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